

ENHANCED INTERFACIAL PROPERTY OF CARBON FIBRE COMPOSITES BASED ON VERTICAL GRAPHENE

Z. Sha^{1*}, Z. Han², S. Wu^{1,3} and C.H. Wang¹

1 School of Mechanical and Manufacturing Engineering, University of New South Wales, Sydney, NSW 2052, Australia.

2 CSIRO Manufacturing, P. O. Box 218, Lindfield, NSW 2070, Australia

3 School of Engineering, Macquarie University, Sydney, NSW 2109, Australia

* Corresponding author (z.sha@unsw.edu.au)

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ABSTRACT

The interfacial interaction between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix is critical to the mechanical performance of fibre-reinforced composites. In this research we graft vertical graphene (VG) on single carbon fibres using plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD). The effects of VGs grafting on carbon fibre surface roughness, wettability, tensile strength, as well as the interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between carbon fibre and epoxy are investigated. Our results show that both the surface roughness and the wettability towards epoxy could be dramatically increased by grafting VGs on carbon fibre surface. Single fibre tensile tests also confirm that the grafting of VG on carbon fibres doesn't degrade the fibre in mechanical strength, while the IFSS of carbon fibre/epoxy composites is significantly improved. This research demonstrates the potential of grafting VGs on CF in improving the mechanical properties of carbon fibre reinforced composites, and also provides possibility to develop multifunctional hierarchical carbon fibre reinforced composites with better performance.

1 INTRODUCTION

Owing to the high strength-to-weight ratio and high resistance to corrosion [1], carbon fibre reinforced composites are widely applied in various areas. In the carbon-epoxy composite system, loads are usually transferred from epoxy matrix to carbon fibre through shear, hence the interfacial interaction between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix is critical to the mechanical and functional properties of fibre-reinforced composites. Strong interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between fibre and matrix is essential to the effective load transfer, which could warrant that most of the loads are sustained by strong carbon fibres rather than epoxy, thus maximizing the mechanical performance of composites. Therefore, in order to develop composites with better performance, it is of great importance to explore effective ways to improve the interfacial properties between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix.

Modifying carbon fibre surface by introducing carbon-based nanomaterials could largely enhance the adhesion between fibre and epoxy matrix, which enables effective stress transfer as well as improved mechanical properties of composites. Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) [2-8] and carbon nanofibres (CNFs) [9-12] are two of the most widely used one-dimensional (1D) nanomaterials to modify the fibre/matrix interface of composites. Owing to the large surface area, rigid tubelike morphology as well as various approaches to enable aligned orientation, CNTs seems to have a better performance in improving the IFSS compared with CNFs. However, most of the IFSS improvements made by CNTs were accompanied by the degradation of tensile strength of carbon fibres, which was probably caused by the surface flaws introduced to the fibre through thermal annealing and surface oxidation during the chemical vapor deposition of CNTs. The graphene nanoplatelets (GNPs) [13, 14] have been regarded as an alternative 2D nanomaterial to modify the fibre/matrix interface considering their strong mechanical stiffness, high Young's modulus, large surface area as well as the cheap production cost compared with CNTs. However, due to the weak alignment control of nanomaterial, the IFSS improvement made by GNPs is quite less significant than which made by CNTs.

In this work we grow vertical graphene (VG) on carbon fibres at relatively low temperature (~400 °C) and short time duration (~20 min) by using plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD). The VGs synthesized in this way are graphene nanoflakes aligned perpendicularly to the carbon fibre surface. By using this method, we can avoid the degradation of carbon fibres and solve

the alignment issue of nanomaterials. The effects of VGs on carbon fibre surface roughness, wettability, tensile strength, and interfacial shear strength (IFSS) between carbon fibre and epoxy are investigated in this research. The results show that both the surface roughness and the wettability of carbon fibre are dramatically increased with VGs grafted on the carbon fibre surface. Single fibre tensile tests also confirm that the grafting of VGs on carbon fibres causes negligible degradation in mechanical strength, while the IFSS of carbon fibre/epoxy composites is significantly improved. This research demonstrates the potential of grafting VGs on carbon fibre in improving the mechanical properties of carbon fibre reinforced composites, and also provides a new way to develop hierarchical carbon fibre reinforced composites with better performance.

2 EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

2.1 Materials

Carbon fibres (CFs) applied in this research were Pyrofil TR50S 15K, which had an average diameter of 7 μm . The VGs were grafted onto carbon fibre surface through plasma-enhanced chemical vapour deposition (PECVD) method. The epoxy resin (Raku Tool EL-2203) was mixed with the curing agent (Raku Tool EH-2970-1) with the ratio of 10:3, which was used as matrix for the wettability and single fibre fragmentation test. The curing process was conducted at room temperature for 24h as well as post curing at 80 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 3h.

2.2 Growth of VGs on CFs

VG was grown by PECVD using methane (CH_4) as the precursor gas, as reported previously [15, 16]. Briefly, single carbon fibres were loaded into a vacuum chamber. The Ar gas was introduced with a flow rate of 10 sccm when the base pressure in chamber reached to 2×10^{-2} Pa. Then the chamber pressure was adjusted to 1.5Pa and Ar plasma was ignited by a 13.56 MHz radio-frequency (RF) power source at 1000 W. This Ar plasma pre-treatment was conducted to clean the carbon fibre surface and provide good adhesion between VG and the carbon fibre in the following deposition process.[17] After 10 min plasma pre-treatment, the growth of VG was started by adding H_2 and CH_4 gases at 20 and 20 sccm respectively. The growth temperature was controlled at ~ 400 $^{\circ}\text{C}$, which was purely provided by plasma heating and no external heating device needed. With 10 min deposition, carbon fibres grafted with VG were obtained for the following experimental work.

2.3 Characterization

2.3.1 Morphology characterization

The heights of VGs grown on the surface of CFs were observed and measured by a scanning electron microscope (FEI Nova NanoSEM 230). The cross-sections of samples with CFs embedded in epoxy matrix were coated with a thin layer of platinum to aid the observation. Raman spectroscopy (Renishaw inVia) was conducted to characterise the VG grafted on CFs.

2.3.2 Surface roughness characterization

The surfaces of the as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres were observed by an atomic force microscope (Bruker Dimension ICON SPM) and their surface roughness were measured in tapping mode. The scanning rate was 0.15Hz and the scanning scope was set to be $4 \mu\text{m} \times 4 \mu\text{m}$. To prepare the sample, a carbon fibre was first attached with two cardboards on each ends and then placed on to a glass plate with its two sides overhanging. The weights of the cardboards attached on each ends of the fibre exert a tensile force to straighten the carbon fibre. Silver glue was then applied on two sides of the glass plate to fix the fibre. After the silver glue cured, the overhang outside the glass plates were cut and then the sample was ready for the surface roughness measurement along the longitudinal direction of the fibre.

2.3.3 Surface wettability

Surface wettability of the as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres were compared by a drop-on-fibre method [18] by measuring the apparent contact angle between epoxy resin micro-droplet and carbon fibre. The epoxy resin was sprayed on the surface of the as received and VGs grafted carbon

fibres, after 24h curing in room temperature, fibres were observed with an Olympus BX53M optical microscope. 30 droplets of each group were chosen and the images were captured to measure the contact angles. The final apparent contact angle of each group was determined as the average measured values of 30 droplets.

2.3.4 Single fibre tensile test

The tensile strength of the as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres were measured in accordance with ASTM C 1577-03, which aim to evaluate the effects of VG growth process on the carbon fibre's tensile strength. Single fibre tensile tests were conducted in a DMA 2980 instrument (TA instrument), which has a load cell of 18N and force resolution of 0.001 N. To prepare the sample, a single carbon fibre was mounted on a thin cardboard support frame containing a 5-mm-long square window which defined the specimen gauge length. The diameter of carbon fibre was measured an Olympus BX53M optical microscope after the fibre mounted on cardboard. Five different areas were measured on each fibre and the average value was calculated to be the fibre diameter. The following equation is used for the calculation of carbon fibre's tensile strength:

$$\sigma = \frac{4F}{\pi d_f^2} \quad (1)$$

where F is the failure load and d_f is the fibre diameter. 30 samples for each group were tested and the calculated tensile strengths were based on the gauge length of 5 mm.

Weibull strength properties for the single fibres were calculated based on the two-parameter Weibull strength distribution [19]:

$$P_F(\sigma, L) = 1 - \exp\left(-\frac{L}{L_0} \left(\frac{\sigma}{\sigma_0}\right)^m\right) \quad (2)$$

where P_F is the cumulative failure probability of fibre at a stress σ and length L , m is the Weibull modulus, σ_0 is the characteristic strength and L_0 is the gauge length. By arranging the tensile strength values of the fibres in ascending order, P_F could be determined using the following method [20]:

$$P_F(\sigma_i) = \frac{i-0.5}{N} \quad (3)$$

where, $P_F(\sigma_i)$ is the probability of failure corresponding to the i -th strength value and N is the total number of fibres tested. With the combination of Equation 2 and Equation 3, the value of m could be obtained by linear regression method.

For tensile strength at a different gauge length L_1 , Equation 2 can be rewritten as:

$$\sigma_0(L_1) = \sigma_0(L_0) \left(\frac{L_0}{L_1}\right)^{1/m} \quad (4)$$

2.3.5 Single fibre fragmentation test

The single fibre fragmentation test was emerged from the early work of Kelly and Tyson [21], which could be used to analyse the interfacial property between fibre and matrix. Each test specimen for the single fibre fragmentation test consists of a single fibre embedded in the epoxy matrix. Elongating the specimen with tensile load will result in fibre breakage, and with the increase of elongation, the amount of fibre fragments will increase as well and finally reach its saturation. The critical fibre fragment length measured at the saturation state can be used to characterize the IFSS between fibre and matrix. Usually a shorter fragment length represents a larger IFSS.

To prepare the test specimens, a carbon fibre was first attached with two cardboards on each ends and then placed into a dogbone-shaped mould with its two sides overhanging outside the mould. The weight of cardboards could guarantee a pre-strain on the fibre and make the fibre straight. The well mixed epoxy resin and hardener were then casted into the mould. After 24 h curing at room temperature and 3 h post curing at 80 °C, samples were ready to be removed from the mould. Before applying load on those samples, necessary grinding and polishing on the surface of the samples were needed to minimize the defect, which was also essential for the optical microscope observation of fibre fragments that followed the fragmentation test. The final dimensions of the sample for fragmentation

test was 2 mm in thickness, 10mm in width and 40mm in length, and the carbon fibre was located at the centre of the sample.

The samples were elongated to reach the saturation of fibre fragments by an Instron 3369 Universal Testing Machine. The micrographs of fibre breakage were recorded with a Leica TCS SP5 microscope under polarizing mode, and lengths of the fibre fragments were measured with image processing software *ImageJ*. The region around the fibre breaks exhibited a coloured pattern under cross-polarised light, which is called photoelastic pattern, and it is helpful to determine the location of fibre breakage.[22] The critical length of fibre fragments was calculated in the following way:

$$l_c = \frac{4}{3} \bar{l} \quad (5)$$

where \bar{l} is the average fragment length, and l_c is the critical length.

This critical length l_c can be used to calculate the IFSS between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix. Owing to VGs grafted on the surface of carbon fibre, the interfacial shear strength we calculated is no longer which between carbon fibre and pure epoxy, but which between carbon fibre and VGs modified epoxy.

With the calculated m and Equation 4 in Section 2.3.3, the tensile strength of fibre at critical length l_c can be obtained as well, and finally the interfacial shear strength between fibre and epoxy resin matrix can be calculated using the following equation:

$$\tau = \frac{\sigma_0(l_c)d_f}{2l_c} \quad (6)$$

where τ is the interfacial shear strength, d_f is the average fibre diameter and $\sigma_0(l_c)$ is fibre's tensile strength at critical length l_c .

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Surface morphology of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres

SEM images were taken on the as received and VGs grafted carbon fibre samples to investigate the morphology change on carbon fibre surface by grafting VGs. As shown in Fig. 1a, the as received carbon fibres have a relatively smooth surface and an average diameter of about 7 μm . Once grafted with a layer of VGs, as shown in Fig. 1b, the surface of carbon fibre became rougher and there is an increase in diameter. The VG height in this research was measured to be about $\sim 4.2 \mu\text{m}$. An open porous network structure of VGs can be clearly visualized in the SEM image of carbon fibre grafted with VGs. This porous structure on hybrid surface warranted a larger contact area with epoxy compared with as received carbon fibres.

Figure 1: SEM images of (a) as received carbon fibre, and (b) carbon fibre grafted with VGs.

3.2 Raman spectroscopy

The Raman spectra of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres are shown in Fig.2. Five

characteristic peaks of graphene, which are D, G, D', 2D, and D+D', could be clearly observed in the Raman spectra of VGs grafted carbon fibre. Typically, the ratio of I_D/I_G is used to evaluate the defects concentration level in the graphitic structure of carbonaceous materials [23]; while the ratio of $I_D/I_{D'}$ could be used to identify the nature of defects in graphene. As reported previously[24], the $I_D/I_{D'}$ ratio at ~ 13 represents a majority of tetrahedral hybridization defects, it will decrease to ~ 7 for vacancy-like defects and reach a minimum of ~ 3.5 for boundary-like defects in the graphene. In this research, the $I_D/I_{D'}$ ratio of VG was ~ 6.9 , indicating that the vacancy-like defects appeared to be dominant. From the Raman spectra, the types of graphene grafted on carbon fibre can be determined as well [25]. As the I_G/I_{2D} ratio is ~ 2.0 , indicating that the VGs in this research are multilayer graphene.

Figure 2: Raman spectra of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres.

3.3 Surface roughness of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres

The surface features of the as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres were characterized by atomic force microscopy (AFM). For the as-received carbon fibre, the surface is relatively smooth and its average roughness is measured to be about 15.9 nm, as shown in Fig. 3a. With VGs grafted on carbon fibre surface, the average surface roughness increased to 191nm, which is more than 12 times larger than that of the as-received carbon fibre, as shown in Fig.3b. This increase in surface roughness is owing to the presence of VGs on the carbon fibre surface. It could be concluded from these AFM results that by grafting VGs on carbon fibre surface, the surface roughness could be largely increased and this increase in surface roughness could potentially improve the adhesion property between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix, which will be explored in the following sections.

Figure 3: AFM results of (a) as received carbon fibre, (b) carbon fibre grafted with VGs.

3.4 Surface wettability of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres

The surface wettability of carbon fibre also plays an important role in determining the interfacial properties of composites [26, 27]. Here, the surface wettability of as received and VGs grafted carbon

fibres were characterized by spraying epoxy resin on carbon fibre and measuring the apparent contact angles of droplets after the epoxy resin cured. Usually, a smaller apparent contact angle is considered to represent a better surface wettability. As shown in Fig.4a, the contact angle of as-received carbon fibre sample is about 51.8°. With VGs grafted on carbon fibre surface, the measured apparent contact angle decreased to 36.1°, as shown in Fig.4b, indicating the surface wettability was improved. Based on these surface wettability results, a positive correlation between surface roughness and wettability was found, which is in line with the early published work, that the effect of surface roughness on the apparent contact angle can be described by the Wenzel equation [29]:

$$\cos \theta_r = r \cos \theta_s \quad (7)$$

where θ_r and θ_s are the apparent contact angles on the rough and smooth surface, and $r > 1$ is the roughness ratio, which is defined as the actual area of a rough surface divided by its projected area. Based on this equation, when $\theta_s < 90^\circ$, an increase in the surface roughness of a sample will result in a decrease in the apparent contact angle between a fibre and epoxy matrix indicating an improvement on surface wettability of the sample.

Figure 4: Contact angles of droplets measured for (a) as received carbon fibre and (b) carbon fibre grafted with VGs.

3.5 Single fibre tensile test

At least 30 specimens of each group were tested in single fibre tensile test and the calculated tensile strengths were based on the gauge length of 5 mm. The mean values of tensile strength for as received and VGs grafted carbon fibres are shown in Fig. 5a, and there is no significant difference between this two groups, which indicates that process we used to graft VGs on carbon fibre doesn't degrade the fibre strength. The statistical analysis of carbon fibre tensile strength was made by applying the two-parameter Weibull distribution, as shown in Equation 2. The Weibull fracture stress distribution was measured for as received single carbon fibres and carbon fibres grafted with VGs. Plots of the natural logs of fracture stress against the probability of failure for as received single carbon fibres and carbon fibres grafted with VGs are shown in Fig. 5b. For gauge length $L_0 = 5$ mm, the value of Weibull modulus m and characteristic strength σ_0 were calculated using the maximum likelihood method with 90% confidence as described in ASTM C1239-13, and values of each group can be found in Fig. 6b as well.

Figure 5: (a) The average tensile strength and (b) the Weibull fracture stress distribution of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibre.

3.6. Single fibre fragmentation test

Specimens were elongated to achieve the saturation of fragments amount. Polarizing optical micrographs were taken for all samples to record the fibre breakage, as shown in Fig.6. An average value of fragments length measured in a gauge length of 16mm for at least 3 specimens was used for calculation. As shown in Fig.6a, the as received carbon fibre had a critical fragment length of about $435.7\ \mu\text{m}$. With VG grafted on carbon fibre surface, the critical fragment length decreased to $224.7\ \mu\text{m}$, which is nearly half that of the as received carbon fibre, as shown in Fig.6b. It is worth noting that there are bright areas with each fibre breakage observed from micrographs of the as-received carbon fibre, which represented the debonding zone between carbon fibre and matrix. However, these debonding zones disappeared after being grafted with VGs. The fracture mode at the carbon fibre / epoxy interface between has also been changed from debonding mode to the crack propagation mode after carbon fibre grafted with VGs. That is, instead of causing serious interface debonding after the fibre is broken at its weakest point, the crack has begun to propagate to the epoxy matrix. This could act as evidence of the improvements made by VGs on the interfacial properties between fibres and matrix. The fragment length distribution of all test specimens is shown in Fig.7a, where it can be seen that carbon fibres grafted with VGs have a much larger concentration of fragment length at about $100\sim 200\ \mu\text{m}$ compared with as received carbon fibres.

Figure 6: Polarizing micrographs of the fibre breakage: (a) as received carbon fibre and (b) carbon fibre grafted with VGs.

The critical tensile strength of the samples was calculated based on Equation 4 by using the critical fragment length obtained as above. After that, the IFSS was calculated by using Equation 6 and the results are presented in Table 1 and Fig.7b. The IFSS of as received carbon fibres is only about 50.9 MPa, after grafting with VGs, a 140% improvement has been achieved and the IFSS increased to about 122.2 MPa. This demonstrates the advantage of grafting VGs on carbon fibre in improving the interfacial shear strength between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix.

Samples	Critical length l_c (μm)	$\sigma_0(l_c)$ (MPa)	IFSS τ (MPa)
As received CF	435.7 ± 4.3	6331.4 ± 10.2	50.9 ± 0.6
CF Grafted with VG	224.7 ± 4.2	7841.2 ± 29.0	122.2 ± 2.8

Table 1: Critical length (l_c), fibre's tensile strength at critical length and interfacial shear strength (τ) for as received carbon fibres and carbon fibres grafted with VGs.

Figure 7: (a) Fragment length distribution and (b) the IFSS of as received and VGs grafted carbon fibre.

To understand the strengthening mechanism, the cross-sectional view of fractured surface of the samples was examined with SEM technique, as shown in Fig.8. It was evident that instead of randomly mixing graphene nanosheets with epoxy matrix, grafting the VGs to modify the epoxy matrix around carbon fibre seems to be more targeted and effective in improving the IFSS between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix. It is obvious from Fig.8b that all the graphene nanosheets are arranged perpendicular to the carbon fibre surface owing to the unique morphology of VGs, which helps building up effective load transferring paths between epoxy matrix and carbon fibre, thus improves the IFSS.

Figure 8: The cross-sectional view of fractured surface fracture surfaces in carbon fibres/epoxy composites: (a) as received carbon fibre, (b) carbon fibre grafted VGs.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In conclusion, we proposed a mild way to graft VGs on carbon fibre surface by PECVD method and investigated the influence of VGs on properties including surface roughness, wettability, fibre's tensile strength and the IFSS between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix. It is evident from the results that the VGs grafted on carbon fibre surface could dramatically increase the surface roughness surface wettability. Owing to the mild growth process of VGs, there was no significant strength degradation found on carbon fibre. The IFSS between carbon fibre and epoxy matrix were found to be improved by grafting VGs on the carbon fibre surface, and a 140% improvement on IFSS has been achieved with $\sim 4.2 \mu\text{m}$ VGs grafted on carbon fibre surface. These results demonstrated the potential of grafting VGs on CF in improving the mechanical properties of carbon fibre reinforced composites, and also pathed new way to develop hierarchical carbon fibre reinforced composites with better performance.

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